

COMPRESSION FAILURE MODES OF CARBON FIBER FABRIC SCRAPS - EPOXY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The composite prepreg waste is still an environmental challenge. In the last decade, several researchers have been studying the recycling and reuse processes of composite components, mainly to use in secondary (non-structural) components. In this paper, uncured aerospace grade prepreg scraps resulted from the production waste were used to manufacture laminates. The carbon reinforcement of the prepreg presented plain weave style fabric. The manufacture used was hand lay-up process positioning the scraps randomly without respecting the preferred directions of the warp and weft. Therefore, the resulting laminate is multidirectional (in the plane) and orthotropic. The cure was performed in autoclave at the maximum temperature of $(180 \pm 1)^\circ\text{C}$ and pressure of 100 psi. This laminate was tested in compression according to standard SACMA SEM 1R-94. The results show an average compression resistance equivalent to that of laminates produced with continuous layers, although with a higher dispersion. In order to understand this variation, the fracture surfaces of the laminates were analyzed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) in order to identify the failure modes. The specimens present shear and interlaminar failure modes, in addition to a mixed mode of failure (a transition between the shear and interlaminar failures). For the same specimen, the analysis of the internal arrangement of the fibers shows that changes in failure modes occur in regions where the carbon fabric is not continuous, i.e. there are junctions of scraps. It was also observed that none of the compression tests resulted in catastrophic failure of the specimens, possibly due to a greater resistance to fracture growth in the presence of mixed failure mode.

1 INTRODUCTION

The compression behavior is a limiting in the design of structures made of carbon fiber reinforced polymers, mainly due to the fact that its compressive strength is about 40% lower than its tensile strength [1]. The fiber-reinforced composites subjected to compressive loads can also exhibit different failure modes [2], and show different aspects and sequence of events to fracture, besides being governed by different properties.

Studies conducted by Argon [3], Odom and Adams [4] and Jelf and Fleck [5] were pioneers in the analysis of the failure modes. The study performed by Odom and Adams [4], for example, mentions the influence of the lateral stability (by changing the tab geometry of the specimen) in the occurrence of the failure mode. Currently, it is possible to use the knowledge about the failure modes as a way to improve the compressive performance of fiber-reinforced composites, as indicated by Pinho et al. [6].

In the last decade, the environmental concerns led to studies of recycling and reuse of fiber-reinforced composites. The concern is even greater with respect to the thermosetting matrix composites, since they cannot be re-melted/softened in contrast to thermoplastic matrices. In addition,

the thermoset matrices commonly used, such as epoxy and polyester, are difficult to depolymerise [7]. Feraboli and coworker [8] for example, investigate the mechanical behavior of carbon fiber/epoxy composites manufactured from chopped unidirectional prepreg. They found that this composite has an “inherent material” stress concentration that arises from its heterogeneous nature.

The objective of this paper is to study the fracture surface of carbon fiber/epoxy composites submitted to compressive loading. The composites used here were made from prepreg scraps, but differently from the work of Feraboli et al. [8], here the scraps were not chopped. Applying the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) technique we could identify the failure modes and the influence of the microstructure in the fracture propagation.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The fiber-reinforced composites used in this study are purposely scraps of aeronautic manufacturing process (usually considered as production waste) which were originally manufactured with aerospace grade carbon fiber (HexTow® AS4-3k, Hexcel Fibers), arranged as plain weave fabric, and impregnated with epoxy matrix (HexPly® F155, Hexcel Composites). In the construction of each lamina, the scraps were positioned side by side to completely fill the required dimensions of the lamina, but without paying attention to the warp and weft directions (Fig. 1), so that the manufacturing may be facilitated. After the laminate lay-up, the cure was performed at $(180 \pm 1)^\circ\text{C}$, 100 psi.

Figure 1: Representation of the layers in the laminate manufactured with prepreg scraps.

After the cure cycle has been completed, the laminates were trimmed on to the compression test specimens observing the SACMA SEM 1R-94 standard. To assess the multidirectional behaviour of the laminate, the specimens were extracted in directions 0° and 90° (15 specimens in each direction). The compression test was carried out until the failure of the specimens, and then, using a scanning electron microscope (TESCAN – Veja 3 XMU) the failure modes were identified using small magnifications. Finally, the fracture surfaces were examined to identify the fracture aspects as to verify how the internal microstructure influenced the fracture propagation.

3 RESULTS

The results of compression strength (mean value \pm standard deviation) are presented in Table 1 in a normalized form. Paiva and coworkers [9] studied the compression behavior of a carbon fiber/epoxy composite manufactured with continuous prepreg of the same type used here. There are no statistically significant differences between the mean compressive strength. Albeit the standard deviation is quite higher for the prepreg scrap composites, i.e. nearly 20% and 60% higher for the 0° and 90° specimens, respectively. Briefly, the compression strength of the prepreg scrap composites is equivalent to the continuous prepreg composites, whilst the higher deviation of results reflects the heterogeneous microstructure of the prepreg scrap composites.

Composites	Compression Strength
0° Specimens	1.048 ± 0.067
90° Specimens	1.016 ± 0.090
Reference [10]	1.000 ± 0.055

Table 1: Comparison between the compression test results and a reference.

3.1 Failure Modes

As previously mentioned, the compression failure of fiber-reinforced polymer composites may occur by a number of modes and for each mode can be assigned a sequence of events that led to failure. A variety of compression failure modes can be found in the literature, not being unusual to find similar failures described and named differently. In this work, we chose to develop a classification that could cover the failure modes already related in the literature for different types of composites. Moreover, this classification can easily include new cases that could be reported. Fig. 2a presents the four failure modes and different aspects that the compression fracture can assume even with the same failure mode. Furthermore, some specimens analysed here shown an irregular fracture propagation in the through-the-width (in plane) direction that lead to a distinction between the failure modes in each side of the specimen, as seen in Fig. 2b. For this reason, the occurrence of the failure modes was accounted on both sides of each sample, i.e. a total of 60 analyses for the 30 specimens.

Figure 2: Classification scheme of the failure modes (a) and representation of occurrence of different failure modes in each side of the specimen (b).

Among the side of the specimens analyzed here, the shear failures were presented in 60% of the total and the fracture aspect of these failures (58% of all the sides of the specimens) was a wedge splitting type of failure. This fracture aspect is unusual for carbon fiber/epoxy composites and was related by Boey and coworkers [10] for wood polymer composites. Fig. 3 presents two of the specimens that fail by wedge splitting. In this case we can see the typical characteristic of this type of failure, i.e. the two cracks propagating by shear within the specimen and forming a wedge when encounters each other. This wedge is responsible for a delamination that propagates from the wedge tip. The specimens also presented flexural damages caused by the slide motions of the mating surfaces, and these damages are a characteristic of the shear failures.

Another failure mode observed in the specimens was the interlaminar failure. This mode of failure occurred in 22% of all the sides of the specimens and the fracture aspect was a delamination buckling [11, 12]. Briefly, the compressive load leads to an interlaminar failure by shear that initiates in the outer layers. The lateral stability of these layers drops sharply causing the buckling. Finally, as the load increases the fracture propagates to the inner layers. In the specimens shown in Fig. 4 one could

see the two major characteristics of this failure mode, i.e. the multiple delaminations and the buckling of individual layers.

Figure 3: Specimens with shear failure mode and fracture aspect of wedge splitting.

Figure 4: Specimens with interlaminar failure mode and fracture aspect of delamination buckling.

Besides these two failure modes, 18% of the sides of the specimens presented a fracture with characteristics of both failure modes. This fracture aspect was denominated by mixed failure mode, as shown in Fig. 5. In this case, it can be seen the characteristics of the two failure modes. As before mentioned, the delamination buckling characteristics are the multiple delaminations and the buckling of the layer (mainly the outer ones), whilst the wedge splitting characteristics are the flexural damages on the fracture surface and the formation of a wedge that lead to a large delamination.

As previously mentioned, another feature observed on some specimens was what we define as multiple failure modes, in other words, the two sides of the same specimen show distinct failure modes. A total of 43% of all specimens analyzed showed this feature. In Fig. 6 it can be seen at the left

and at the right the two sides of the same specimen, where there is a clear difference between the failure modes presented by each side. At the center of Fig. 6 the fracture surfaces are shown and it is possible to see that there is a point coincident in the upper and lower part of the specimen, indicated in the figure, where a shift occurred in the fracture propagation.

Figure 5: Specimens with mixed failure mode and fracture aspects of wedge splitting and delamination buckling.

Figure 6: Fracture surfaces of a specimen that presented multiple failure modes.

In order to understand the shift in the fracture propagation, higher magnifications were used at this region (see Figure 7). The upper and lower parts are shown in Fig. 7a and Fig. 7b, respectively. It can be seen in the region that promotes the shift in the fracture propagation what appears to be a discontinuity in the layers. Likely, this discontinuity was caused by two prepreg scraps that were positioned side-by-side, but with considerably difference in the warp and weft direction. Hence, during the compression test, occurred a stress concentration in this region of discontinuity that led to a

shifting of the fracture propagation direction. Furthermore, the difference in the warp and weft direction of these neighboring layers promotes a distinct mechanical response for the two sides of the specimen, what finally caused the occurrence of the multiple failure modes. These observations agree with the hypothesis that the heterogeneous microstructure of the prepreg scraps composites promotes the higher standard deviation presented in the compressive strength measurements.

Figure 7: Detailed microstructure of the upper (a) and lower (b) part of the specimen in the region that caused the shift in the fracture propagation.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the compressive behaviour of carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates was studied. These laminates were manufactured using prepreg scraps from the aeronautical production waste. The results of the compression test show that the average compressive strength of the prepreg scrap composites is similar to that of composites manufactured with continuous prepreps. However, the deviation of the compressive strength is considerably higher for the prepreg scrap composites.

After the compression test, the specimens were observed using a scanning electron microscope to assess the compressive failure mode. The shear failure was the most frequent and presented a fracture aspect of a wedge that led to a large delamination. Some specimens exhibited an interlaminar failure where it was possible to see multiple delaminations and the buckling of some layers. Finally, in some specimens it was possible to see the characteristics of more than one failure mode, what was defined as mixed failure mode. Furthermore, in a large quantity of specimens the fracture propagation was irregular which led to the two sides of the specimens to present different failure modes. The analyses of the microstructure show that the cause of this shifting in the fracture propagation was a junction of scraps with different warp and weft directions that led to a stress concentration within the specimen.

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